

NOTES ON THE *TANTRAYUKTI-S*

INDIANS tried to analyse the formal elements which gave form to a scientific work (*tantra*), in the same way that they tried to analyse the elements of a debate (*vāda*); for practical usage they collected these elements in lists and explained them. These rules for the composition of scientific works date back to a time as early as the *vāda*-doctrine. But, whereas at least two traditions may be established for the *vāda*-doctrine,¹ only a single form of tradition seems to have existed for the *tantrayukti-s*. Both the *Carakasamhitā*, containing a short enumeration of the terms that belong to the *tantrayukti-s*, and Suśruta and Kauṭilya, who provide not only this enumeration but also a definition and short explanation of these terms, agree to such an extent with one another, that we are justified in speaking of one single tradition.² The following table will illustrate the relationships of these three versions of lists of terms with one another.³

¹ One *vāda*-tradition leading over Caraka to the *Nyāyasūtra-s* and the other that is to be found in the Buddhistic *vāda*-compendiums as for instance the *Prayogasāra*. Cf. G. Oberhammer: 'Ein Beitrag zu den Vāda-Traditionen Indiens', *WZKSO* 7, 1963, pp. 63-103.

² This seems to pass, however, only for the old period.

³ The *tantrayukti-s* are to be found in *Carakasamhitā*, *Siddhisthānam* 12, 69c-77b, *Suśrutasaṃhitā*, *Uttaratāntram* 65, *Kauṭilya-Arthaśāstram* 15. 1. 1-70.

The article by W. Ruben: 'Zur Frühgeschichte der indischen Philosophie—Beiträge zur Literaturwissenschaft und Geistesge-

TERM	TRANSLATION	IN:
1. <i>adhikaraṇam</i>	topic	K(1) S(1) C(1)
2. <i>vidhānam</i>	statement of contents	K(2) S(21) C(21)
3. <i>yogaḥ</i>	employment	K(3) S(2) C(2)
4. <i>padārthaḥ</i>	meaning of word	K(4) S(3) C(4)
5. <i>hetvarthaḥ</i>	reason	K(5) S(4) C(3)
6. <i>uddeśaḥ</i>	mention	K(6) S(5) C(6)
7. <i>nirdeśaḥ</i>	exposition	K(7) S(6) C(7)
8. <i>upadeśaḥ</i>	advice	K(8) S(7) C(10)
9. <i>apadeśaḥ</i>	reference	K(9) S(8) C(11)

schichte Indiens', *Festgabe Hermann Jacobi*, Bonn, 1926, pp. 346-57—in its main arguments superseded by later studies—has valuable suggestions for the question of the *tantrayukti-s* in regard to the knowledge of the material and some individual points. Kauṭilya's *tantrayukti-s*, however, do not seem to have been 'eine [zwecklose] Erfindung dieses denkerisch veranlagten Staatsmannes' (p. 352), as Ruben wants to have it. The very fact that the connection of the doctrine of the *tantrayukti-s* with the work of Kauṭilya is very loose points against his authorship. The only purpose of the chapter can be to show that the work of Kauṭilya, the *Arthaśāstra*, was composed 'according to the rules'. In this sense Kauṭilya begins his exposition of the *tantrayukti-s* with the words *tad* (= *śāstram*) *dvātriṃśad'yuktīyuktam* (*AŚ* 15. 1. 3) and ends with the statement *evam śāstram idaṃ yuktam etābhis tantrayuktibhiḥ . . .* (*AŚ* 15. 1.71). He establishes each of his *tantrayukti-s* with an example of his work. This is exactly the same method as used by the author of the *Yuktidīpikā* some centuries later. Cf. *YD*, p. 2,9-5,21. This purpose, however, can be fulfilled only if the *tantrayukti-s* were for him given rules for the composition of scientific works. Ruben's hypothesis of a historical descent of the three versions starting with Kauṭilya—over Suśruta—to Caraka may still be sustained, although the grouping of Caraka must be left open because adequate definitions are missing. The selection of the deviating categories only is of no significance here. Nevertheless we have adopted the grouping that Ruben had suggested for the three versions.

TERM	TRANSLATION	IN:
10. <i>atideśaḥ</i>	application	K(10) S(10) C(12).
11. <i>pradeśaḥ</i>	indication	K(11) S(9) C(5)
12. <i>upamānam</i>	analogy	K(12) — —
13. <i>arthāpattiḥ</i>	implication	K(13) S(13) C(13).
14. <i>saṃśayaḥ</i>	doubt	K(14) S(24) C(24).
15. <i>prasaṅgaḥ</i>	similar consequence	K(15) S(15) C(15).
16. <i>viparyayaḥ</i>	contrary	K(16) S(14) C(19).
17. <i>vākyaśeṣaḥ</i>	completion of a sentence	K(17) S(12) —
18. <i>anumatam</i>	agreement	K(18) S(20) C(22).
19. <i>vyākhyānam</i>	explication	K(19) S(25) C(23).
20. <i>nirvacanam</i>	derivation of a word	K(20) S(27) C(31)
21. <i>nidarśanam</i>	illustration	K(21) S(28) C(30).
22. <i>apavargaḥ</i>	exception	K(22) S(11) C(18).
23. <i>svasamjñā</i>	one's own technical term	K(23) S(26) C(27).
24. <i>pūrvapakṣaḥ</i>	provisional view	K(24) S(18) C(20).
25. <i>uttarapakṣaḥ</i>	final view	K(25) — —
26. <i>ekāntaḥ</i>	generally valid sentence	K(26) S(16) C(16).
27. <i>anāgatāvekṣaṇam</i>	reference to a future statement	K(27) S(22) C(26).
28. <i>atīkrāntāvekṣaṇam</i>	reference to a past statement	K(28) S(23) C(25).
29. <i>niyogaḥ</i>	restriction	K(29) S(29) C(32).
30. <i>vikalpaḥ</i>	option	K(30) S(30) C(33).
31. <i>samuccayaḥ</i>	combination	K(31) S(31) C(29).
32. <i>ūhyam</i>	what is understood	K(32) S(32) C(28).
33. <i>anaikāntaḥ</i>	not generally valid sentence	— S(17) C(17).
34. <i>pratyuṣaraḥ</i>	opposition	— — C(34).
35. <i>uddhāraḥ</i>	refutation	— — C(35).
36. <i>sambhavaḥ</i>	union	— — C(36).
37. <i>vākyadoṣaḥ</i>	fault of argumentation	— — C(8)
38. <i>prayojanam</i>	purpose	— — C(9)
39. <i>nirṇayaḥ</i>	decision	— S(19) C(14)

With regard to its purpose and awareness of the problems, the doctrine of the *tantrayukti-s* does not essentially differ from the presentations of the *vāda*-doctrine. Only a difference in the subject-matter—on the one hand, we have the spoken language of the debate, and on the other hand, the written composition of a scientific work—causes the difference of the topics dealt with. The *tantrayukti-s*, again similar to the *vāda*-doctrines, had their influence on later times, without which the written, scientific style of the classical period in India would be hard to understand.

The parallelism of the *tantrayukti-s* and the *vāda*-doctrine shows itself not only with regard to the problems and the approach to them, but also in the fact that certain terms appear in both traditions. The mutual influence of the two doctrines can be ascertained in historical times; a fact which can only be hinted at here.¹

Thus we may show as a typical example the use of *tantrayukti-s* for a definition of *vāda*-categories in several passages of the *Nyāyasūtra-s*. In *NS* I. 1. 33 the *pratijñā* is defined as *sādhyānirdeśaḥ*. *Nirdeśaḥ*, again, is a technical term of the *tantrayukti-s*, which is defined by Kautilya as *vyāsavākyaṃ*, ‘ a detailed presentation ’, and contrasts with *uddeśaḥ*, which is defined by him as *samāsavākyaṃ*. Thus the formulation of *NS* I. 1. 33 gains a content historically more concrete, and is

¹ Cf. Ruben, loc. cit., pp. 351 ff., passim.

obviously to be interpreted in the sense of 'a detailed presentation of the things to be proved'.

In a similar way we find in the definition of the *nigamanam* NS I. 1. 39 the term *apadeśaḥ* used in the technical sense of the *tantrayukti-s*. *Apadeśaḥ* is described by Kautilya with the words *evam asāv āheti*, i.e. as a reference to an authority. With Suśruta the motivating character of the term *apadeśaḥ* is even more explicit, when he defines: *anena kāraṇena ity apadeśaḥ*. NS I. 1. 39: *hetvapadesāt pratijñāyāḥ punarvacanam nigamaṇam* is, therefore, interpreted historically, to be rendered in the following way: 'A conclusion is the repetition of a statement on the strength of a [motivating] reference to the reason.'¹ We find the same use of the root *apadīś-* in the sense of the *tantrayukti-s* in the definition of the fallacious reason, which is called *prakaraṇasamaḥ*: *yasmāt prakaraṇacintā sa nirṇayārtham apadiśtaḥ prakaraṇasamaḥ*.² Finally we may refer to the definition of the means of cognition, *śabdaḥ*, in NS I. 1. 7, which is defined as *āptopadeśaḥ* using the *tantrayuktiḥ*: *upadeśaḥ*. However, *upadeśaḥ* is defined by Kautilya as *evam vartitavyam iti upadeśaḥ*.³ This is also followed in Suśruta's definition *evam ity upadeśaḥ*. The *āptopadeśaḥ* may therefore be interpreted here as the teaching of a competent person in the sense of how to behave, and not so much in

¹ This meaning of 'motivating reference' shows the historical link to the use of the term *apadeśaḥ* for the logical reason (*hetuḥ*) in the Vaiśeṣika-system, which has preserved another *tantrayukti* as the name of the example of the proof, i.e. *nidarśanam*.

² NS, I. 1. 7.

³ AŚ, 15. 1. 19.

the sense of a theoretical instruction. Adding to these examples those of the *tantrayukti-s* which appear as separate items in the table of categories of the *vāda*-doctrine or of the *Nyāyasūtra-s* respectively, namely *upamānam*, *arthāpattiḥ*, *saṁśayaḥ*, *nirṇayaḥ*, *prayojanam* and *vākyadoṣaḥ*, one finds the close relationship between the two traditions becoming even more obvious.

The development of the doctrine of the *tantrayukti-s* remains largely in the dark. A discussion of the *tantrayukti-s* in the *Yuktidīpikā*,¹ a work written approximately in the 6th century A.D., which I had the privilege of reading for the first time with the scholar in whose honour this volume is being brought out, shows, however, that these were still important for the composition of a scientific work. In order to prove that his work is of a scientific character the author puts himself the question: *ke tantraguṇāḥ kiyanto vā*, and he answers it with the following lines:

*sūtrapramāṇāvayavopapattir
anyūnatā saṁśayanirṇayoktiḥ¹
uddeśanirdeśam anukramas ca
saṁjñōpadeśāv iti tantrasaṁpat ||²*

¹ Published for the first time by Pulinbehari Chakravarti as no. 23 of the Calcutta Sanskrit Series, Calcutta, 1938. A second edition based on two further manuscripts by Ram Chandra Pandeya appeared under the title: *Yuktidīpikā*, an ancient Commentary on the *Sāṁkhya-Kārikā* of Īśvarakṛṣṇa, Delhi—Varanasi—Patna, 1967. As the first edition is out of print for a long time the quotations will be given according to this edition, thereafter abridged as *YD*.

² *YD*, p. 2, 10-12.

and comprehensive presentation of the *tantrayukti-s*, even though the author mentions other *tantrayukti-s* later. He starts his discussion with the words *ke tantraguṇāḥ* and he finishes it with the words *ete sūtropapattyādayas tantraguṇāḥ*.¹ Thus we have proved this section a close unit, the more as the author of the *Yuktidīpikā* uses in it—quite on purpose—the term *tantraguṇāḥ*, that deviates from the usual term *tantrayuktiḥ*. In the following mention of further *tantrayukti-s*, however, he sticks to the traditional term *tantrayuktiḥ*. In addition to this he brings occasionally within those parts dedicated to the *tantraguṇa-s* a wider discussion or at least an exact definition of the *tantraguṇa-s* in question. Where he mentions, however, the traditional *tantrayukti-s*, he confines himself to a simple statement.

There should be no doubt therefore that the doctrine of the *tantraguṇa-s*, as appearing in the lines quoted above, springs from a definite source, which must have given a presentation of these terms in a manner deviating from the old list. It is therefore useful to put together the definitions given by the author of the *Yuktidīpikā*, which seem to go back to this source, and to compare them with the old definitions.

1. *sūtram*: First the author gives the definition of the term: *sūcanāt sūtram; sūcayati tāṃs tān arthaviśeṣān iti sūtram*.² To this definition he adds two verses that contain the characteristics of a *sūtra* as an evidence:

¹ *YD*, p. 2, 10 and *YD*, p. 5, 15.

² *YD*, p. 2, 18.

apunaruktam asanāṅganāṅi saravāḍa vsvavomānāṅi 1
astobham anavadyam ca sūtram sūtravido viduḥ 11

It is worth noting that the author thought it necessary to comment on the term *astobham* with the word *apunaruktam*. Basically the second verse has the same content as the first:

laghūni sūcitārthāni svalpākṣarapadāni ca 1
sarvataḥ sārabhūtāni sūtrāny āhur manīṣiṅaḥ 11 1

The appearing of a *sūtra* (*sūtropapattiḥ*) as a demanded quality for a scientific work cannot be found in the traditional list of the *tantrayukti-s*. This is a specific innovation of the doctrine of the *tantrayukti-s*, a change that indicates clearly a new aspect of the scientific production. The free development of a doctrine, evident from the revisions and redactions of the *sūtra-s* of the various schools, has given way to a development of the doctrine characterized by commenting on authoritarian basic texts. References to the *sūtra* have become necessary stylistic elements of a scientific work.

2. *pramāṇāvayavopapattiḥ*: Similarly we do not find a model for the existence of means of cognition (*pramāṇāni*) and proof (*avayavāḥ*) in the older treatment of the *tantrayukti-s*, even though the inclusion of these

¹ *FD*, p. 2, 23 and 26 f.; both verses are also quoted by Vācaspatimīśra in his *Nyāyavārttikatātparyāṅikā* (Calcutta Sanskrit Series 18, p. 70, 13 f. and 16 f.). It is obvious that the *Yukti-dīpikā* which he quotes as *Rājavārttikam* (*Sāṃkhyatattvakaumudī*, Calcutta Sanskrit Series 15, p. 115, 15) is his source in this case.

two groups of problems in the doctrine of the *tantrayukti-s* was made easier by certain *tantrayukti-s*, which may be regarded as first steps in the scope of this doctrine. The author of the *Yuktidīpikā* neither gives definitions of the means of cognition nor of the individual members of a proof; instead, he refers to the treatment of these problems within the frame of his work. In this case the school-doctrine had evidently gone beyond the rather archaic definitions of the *tantraguṇa-s*.

3. *anyūnatā*: The definition passed on by the author of the *Yuktidīpikā* runs: *padārthakārtsnyam aśeṣatānyūnatā*.¹ Earlier we find the *anyūnatā* only as a subgroup of the *vāda*-category *vākyaprasāṃsā* but not as one of the *tantrayukti-s*.² In the doctrine of the *tantraguṇa-s* we find it as the demand for the complete treatment of the subjects of the scientific work in question.

4. *saṃśayanirṇayoktiḥ*: The term *saṃśayaḥ*, defined as *sāmānyābhīdhānam saṃśayaḥ*³ in the doctrine of the *tantraguṇa-s*, appears in the traditional list of the *tantrayukti-s* in all three versions, though Kauṭilya and Suśruta see it differently with regard to its essence. Kauṭilya has *ubhayato hetumān arthaḥ saṃśayaḥ*,⁴ while Suśruta gives the definition in the form *ubhayaheturdarśanam saṃśayaḥ*. On the other hand, the definition of *saṃśayaḥ*, as it can be found in the doctrine of the *tantraguṇa-s*, corresponds clearly to the possibility of

¹ *YD*, p. 4, 14.

² Cf. *Carakasamhitā*, Vim. sthānam 8, 54 f., where it is treated in relation to the proof only.

³ *YD*, p. 4, 24.

⁴ *AS*, 15. 1. 32.

doubt that is the first mentioned in *NS* I. 1. 23 within the *saṃśaya*-definition, which is: *samānānekadharmopapattē . . . viśeṣāpekṣo vimarśaḥ saṃśayaḥ*. The expression *viśeṣāpekṣaḥ* used in this definition refers quite clearly to the *nirṇayaḥ* in the sense of the definition of the term in the *tantraguṇa*-doctrine. There the definition of this term is *viśeṣābhidhānam nirṇayaḥ*.¹

Apart from *Suśruta* we do not come across the concept of the *nirṇayaḥ* in the old tradition of the *tantrayukti*-s. *Suśruta*, however, defines the *nirṇayaḥ* as *tasya* (= *pūrvapakṣasya*) *uttaram*, so that it does not become a complementary term to *saṃśayaḥ*—as the doctrine of the *tantraguṇa*-s has it—but to *pūrvapakṣaḥ*. Nor does the *nirṇayaḥ* of the *Nyāyasūtra*-s, which is defined in *NS* I. 1. 41 with the words *vimṛśya pakṣapratipakṣābhyām arthāvadhāraṇam*, seem to correspond to this concept of the *nirṇayaḥ* as a counterpart to *saṃśayaḥ*. The concept given by the doctrine of the *tantraguṇa*-s rather seems to have had its model in an older form of this topic, which again is indicated by the remark *viśeṣāpekṣo vimarśaḥ* in *NS* I. 1. 41. This is strengthened by the fact that the given *nirṇaya*-definition of the *Nyāyasūtra*-s may be connected with regard to its wording *vimṛśya pakṣapratipakṣābhyām* not so much with the definition of the *tarkaḥ*—to which it is the complementary concept—as with the *saṃśaya*-definition. Thus the same polarity *saṃśayaḥ-nirṇayaḥ* which we find in the *tantraguṇa*-doctrine would emerge.

¹ *YD*, p. 4, 25.

5. *uddeśaḥ* and *nirdeśaḥ*: Clearly both these terms have their origin in the tradition of the *tantrayukti-s*. The definition passed down by the author of the *Yuktidīpikā* runs: *saṃkṣepavacanam uddeśaḥ*.¹ This corresponds exactly to Kauṭilya's *samāsavākyaṃ uddeśaḥ*,² a definition that can be found in Suśruta in the form *samāsakathanam uddeśaḥ*. There is even a verbal agreement with Suśruta in regard to the definition of the term *nirdeśaḥ* that is defined by the author of the *Yuktidīpikā* as *vistaravacanam nirdeśaḥ*.³ Suśruta defines the *nirdeśaḥ* in the same way as *vistaravacanam*. Furthermore an agreement in meaning with Kauṭilya, who has the probably older form *vyāsavākyaṃ*⁴ can be noted.

In the case of the two terms *uddeśaḥ* and *nirdeśaḥ* we have—by a lucky coincidence—an interesting piece of evidence that shows that the method of presentation appropriate to these two terms, namely enumeration of the subjects to be treated and afterwards a detailed discussion of the same, was differentiated by other teachers in other ways.—Here, however, the doctrine of the *tantraguṇaḥ* goes directly back to the old tradition of the *tantrayukti-s*, as can be seen from the almost similar definition.—Pakṣilasvāmin, in his *Nyāyabhāṣya*, makes the following remark on the method of presentation, which he uses in accordance with the *Nyāya-sūtra-s*: *trividhā cāsyā śāstrasya pravṛttiḥ, uddeśo lakṣaṇaṃ parīkṣā ceti. tatra nāmadheyena padārthamātrasyābhīdhānam*

¹ *YD*, p. 4, 31.

³ *YD*, p. 5, 1.

² *AS*, 15. 1. 15.

⁴ *AS*, 15. 1. 17.

*uddeśaḥ. tatroddeśasya tattvavyavacchedako dharmo lakṣaṇam. lakṣitasya yathālakṣaṇam upapadyate na veti pramāṇair avadhāraṇaṃ parīkṣā.*¹ It is obvious that this is the same problem as in the case of the *tantrayukti-s*. It cannot be decided, however, whether these three terms, *uddeśaḥ*, *lakṣaṇam*, and *parīkṣā*, stem from an unknown *tantrayukti*-tradition or whether they are a special form developed in the Nyāya. No doubt, these three terms must have developed out of the pair *uddeśaḥ-nirdeśaḥ* by differentiating the *vistaravacanam* of the *nirdeśaḥ* in *lakṣaṇam* and *parīkṣā* according to its content.

6. *anukramah*: This *tantrayukti*, whose definition in the doctrine of the *tantraguṇa-s* is *padārthānām ānupūrvyā samniveśopadeśo 'nukramah*,² forms a clear further step in the development of the term *vidhānam* which we find in all three versions of the *tantrayukti-s*. Kautīlya defines this term as *śāstrasya prakaraṇānupūrvī*.³ The same definition, only slightly altered, may be found in Suśruta as *prakaraṇānupūrvyābhīhitam vidhānam*, where we can see that the wording of this definition comes closer to that in the *tantraguṇa*-doctrine. Another indication of this close relationship to Suśruta is the term *padārthaḥ* as it is used by the *tantraguṇa*-doctrine to define *anukramah*. This term has to be understood in the sense of the Suśruta-definition *yo 'rtho 'bhīhitah sūtre pade vā sa padārthaḥ* and not in the sense of the Kautīlya-definition, according to which *padārthaḥ* has to be taken

¹ *Nyāyabhāṣya*, Poona, 1939, p. 10, 2-4.

² *YD*, p. 5, 3.

³ *AS*, 15. 1. 6.

as *padāvadhikāḥ*.¹ It is interesting to note that in both the *tantraguṇa*-doctrine and in Suśruta, *padārthaḥ* is used in about the same sense as in *NS* I. 1. 1.

7. *saṃjñā*: This term has only a weak equivalent in the term *svasaṃjñā* that appears in the three old versions of the *tantrayukti*-s. But unlike *saṃjñā* in the *tantraguṇa*, *svasaṃjñā* in the *tantrayukti* is essentially related to its own system. Thus Kauṭilya defines it as *parair asamitaḥ śabdaḥ*,² while Suśruta renders the same idea with the words *anyaśāstrāsāmānyā svasaṃjñā*.

However, the definition *saṃjñīpratyāyanārthaḥ śabdaḥ saṃjñā*,³ given in the *tantraguṇa*-doctrine, does not know this attempt at a definition but it takes up a remark in Patañjali's *Mahābhāṣya*. For there we find the following definition: *yayā pratyāyyante sā saṃjñā, ye pratīyante te saṃjñīna iti*.⁴ The subdivision of the term *saṃjñā* also points to the direction of the linguistic analysis of the grammarians rather than to that of the *tantrayukti*-s. For, the discussion of the two subgroups of the *saṃjñā* runs: *sā ca dvividhā. arthanibandhanā svarūpanibandhanā ca. tatrārthanibandhanārthavaśenārthakriyāpekṣā. jātyādyarthasvarūpāntarbhāvī yathārthas tathābhūtam eva saṃjñīnam pratyāyayati. tad yathā pācako lāvaka iti. svarūpanibandhanā punaḥ saṃjñīpratyāyanopāyamātram. svarūpamātropakārīṇī vināvayavārtham samayavaśād atathābhūtam apī saṃjñīnam pratyāyayati. tad yathā gajakarṇo 'śvakarṇa iti*.⁵

¹ *AS*, 15. 1. 10.

² *AS*, 15. 1. 51.

³ *YD*, p. 5, 5.

⁴ *Mahābhāṣya*, ed. Kielhorn, vol. I, p. 38, 20 f.

⁵ *YD*, p. 5, 5-9.

This disposition reminds us of Patañjali's four groups of words: *catuṣṭayī śabdānāṃ pravṛttiḥ, jātiśabdā guṇaśabdāḥ kriyāśabdā yadycchāśabdāś caturthāḥ*,¹ for *jātiḥ* in the expression *jātyādyarthasvarūpāntarbhāvi* has certainly no reference to a philosophical table of categories, but much rather to theories of the kind of Patañjali's four groups of words. In addition to this, the division of the *saṃjñā* into one that is *arthanibandhanā* and one that is *svarūpanibandhanā* could indicate that within the *tantraguṇa*-doctrine the last category of words in Patañjali, namely the proper names, has been absorbed in the group of the *svarūpanibandhanā saṃjñā*. The *arthanibandhanā saṃjñā* then coincides only with the first three categories.

8. *upadeśaḥ*: This last *tantraguṇa* also has an equivalent in the three versions of the old *tantrayukti-s*. Kauṭilya defines this term as *evam vartitavyam ity upadeśaḥ*.² It cannot be decided with certainty whether Suśruta in his definition *evam ity upadeśaḥ* altered the text on purpose by using *upadeśaḥ* in a less concrete sense. It might be possible that he wanted to save this term thereby from a restriction to the meaning 'prescription'. In any case it is a fact that the *tantraguṇa*-doctrine in the *Yuktidīpikā* in its definition *itikartavyatāphalasamākhyanam upadeśaḥ*³ with the words *itikartavyatā-* takes up Kauṭilya's definition. At the same time, however, it goes beyond Kauṭilya's definition by

¹ *Mahābhāṣya*, vol. I, p. 19, 20.

² *AS*, 15. 1. 19.

³ *YD*, p. 5, 12.

transferring the weight from the meaning 'prescription' (*evam vartitavyam*) to that of 'instruction' in regard to the matters that result from a prescription (*phala-samākhyānam*). This enlargement of the meaning of the term *upadeśaḥ* could already have had its model in the conception of Suśruta or in one similar to his.

Thus we have discussed the doctrine of the *tantra-guṇa-s* as found in the *Yuktidīpikā*. The relationship to the old tradition of the *tantrayukti-s* is beyond doubt, both in regard to its purpose as formal elements—which are to guarantee the perfectness (*sam̐pat*) of a scientific work—and in regard to the selection of certain terms and the concrete form of their definitions. On the other hand we have also seen great deviations from the old tradition of the *tantrayukti-s*. They are obviously due to a development of the old doctrine, possibly under the influence of the *vāda*-tradition, leading from Caraka to the *Nyāyasūtra-s*, and—in the particular problem of the term *saṃjñā*—under the influence of grammar.

The influence of grammar in the problems of the *tantrayukti-s* may be shown by yet another example. After the doctrine of the *tantraguṇa-s* the author of the *Yuktidīpikā* adds the following remark: *itikaraṇam prakārārtham; evaṃprakārā anye 'pi draṣṭavyāḥ, tad yathā utsargo 'pavādo 'tideśa ityādiḥ*. As in the case of the *tantraguṇa-s* the author exemplifies each of these terms—though without giving a definition—and closes this discussion with the words *iti evam anyā api tantrayuktayaḥ*

*śakyā iha pradarsāyitum.*¹ Apart from *atideśaḥ* these terms, obviously regarded by the author of the *Yuktidīpikā* as *tantrayukti-s*, are not to be found in the old tradition of the *tantrayukti-s*. They are, however, to be found in grammar, for instance in Patañjali's *Mahābhāṣya*: *kathaṃ tarhīme śabdāḥ pratipattavyāḥ, kimcit sāmānyaviśeṣaval lakṣaṇaṃ pravartyaṃ yenālpena yatnena mahato mahataḥ śabdaughān pratipadyeran. kiṃ punas tat. utsargāpavādau. kaścīd utsargaḥ kartavyaḥ kaścīd apavādaḥ. kathaṃ-jāṭiyakaḥ punar utsargaḥ kartavyaḥ kathaṃjāṭiyako 'pavādaḥ. sāmānyenotsargaḥ kartavyaḥ. tad yathā karmaṇaṃ. tasya viśeṣeṇāpavādaḥ. tad yathā āto 'nupasarge kaḥ.*²

A comparison of the two terms *utsargaḥ* and *apavādaḥ* in the *Yuktidīpikā* makes it clear that the terms in the two texts are identical: *tatrotsargaḥ prakṛtīvirūpaṃ vyaktam, sarūpaṃ cety apavādaḥ, tadviparīta ity utsargaḥ, tathā ca pumān ity apavādaḥ.*³ The term *atideśaḥ* may have come from either the grammar or the tradition of the *tantrayukti-s*; this, however, is only in the conception of Kautīlya, who defines this term with the words *uktēna sādhanam atideśaḥ.*⁴ As yet another reminiscence of the grammar, the expression *itikaraṇaṃ prakārārtham* with which the discussion of these three additional terms starts,⁵ may be mentioned. It reminds us of

¹ *YD*, p. 5, 16 ff.

² *Mahābhāṣya*, vol. I, p. 6, 3-7.

³ *YD*, p. 5, 17-19. The examples in these lines are taken from *Sāṃkhyakārikā* 8 and 11.

⁴ *AŚ*, 15. 1. 23. Suśruta has changed the meaning of this term when he defines: *prakṛtasyānāgatena sādhanam atideśaḥ.*

⁵ *YD*, p. 5, 16.

Kātyāyana's third *vārttika* to Pāṇini I. 1. 44: *itikaraṇo 'rthanirdeśārthaḥ*.¹ The definition of the *Yuktidīpikā* is also found in the *Kāśikā*: *itikaraṇaḥ prakārārthaḥ*.²

All this gives the impression that at the latest at the time of the *Yuktidīpikā* certain terms of grammar, that had a function similar to that of the *tantrayukti-s*, were also regarded as *tantrayukti-s*, whose selection no more seemed to coincide with the old tradition.

In the present state of knowledge about the material it is not yet possible to write a final study on the origin and development of the doctrine of the *tantrayukti-s*. The hope remains, however, that these notes on the *tantrayukti-s* presented here may be a modest addition to our knowledge of these concepts, which, once completely investigated, will let us see the principles of literary scientific composition in the India of the classic period.

¹ *Mahābhāṣya*, vol. I, p. 102, 3.

² *Kāśikā*, V. 2.93.